

Research article

Developing and validating a modelling approach linked with ion selective electrodes to control pollution of water resources from greenhouse crops

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ABSTRACT

The recycling of drainage solution (DS) in greenhouses by applying closed-loop soilless cropping systems (CLS) eliminates pollution of aquifers by nitrogen and phosphorus emissions. However, the variable nutrient composition of the DS poses a significant challenge to its recycling in CLS. To address this challenge, a strategy was developed, based on daily monitoring of macronutrient concentrations in the DS using ion-selective electrodes (ISE) coupled with a modelling approach applied through a decision support system (DSS). The ISE measurements were input data for the DSS to calculate appropriate rates of different single-fertiliser concentrated solutions for automatic injection into a mixture of DS and raw water. The fertiliser injection rates were transmitted online to a fertigation system equipped with nine different single-fertiliser concentrated solutions and were applied automatically in real time. The objective was to maintain the root-zone nutrient concentrations within an optimal range. To test this technology and to validate the modelling approach applied through this DSS, tomato was grown in a CLS with daily measurement of NO_3^- , K^+ , Ca^{2+} , and Na^+ concentrations in the DS using ISEs. The accuracy of the ISEs was confirmed by comparing their measurements with those from standard laboratory procedures in the same samples. The model approach successfully maintained the target nutrient concentrations in the root zone and increased fruit yield by 7.6 % and the agronomic efficiency of nitrogen by 23 %. The proposed technology is expected to encourage the adoption of CLS by growers thus minimising environmental impacts from greenhouse crops.

1. Introduction

Soilless culture has become the primary method for cultivation in modern “high tech” greenhouses due to several advantages, which mostly result in higher yields per unit area and superior quality compared to crops grown in the soil (Fussy and Papenbrock, 2022; Wu et al., 2023). Furthermore, soilless culture also provides substantial benefits for the environment, as it can appreciably reduce or even eliminate contamination of surface and ground water by nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P) emissions. This is achieved by collecting and recycling the fertigation effluent, i.e. the drainage solution (DS) using closed-loop soilless culture systems (CLS). These systems can reduce water and fertiliser consumption by over 30 % and 40 %, respectively (Grewal et al., 2010; Massa et al., 2011; Savvas and Gruda, 2018). The European Green Deal has set a target of a 50 % reduction in nutrient losses, and a 20 % reduction in fertiliser consumption by 2030

(European Green Deal, 2019). CLS can play an important role in achieving these targets while ensuring high crop productivity. In some European countries, such as The Netherlands, recycling of DS in soilless culture systems will be mandatory after 2027 to control contamination of water resources (Van der Salm et al., 2020).

The savings in water use that can be achieved by incorporating CLS into greenhouse production is an international priority. Particularly in the Mediterranean Basin, but also in many drier regions around the world, limited supplies of water for irrigation, due to low and infrequent precipitation and high evaporative demand, are a common and increasing problem (Taft, 2015; Masia et al., 2018). Greenhouse production using CLS is an effective method for saving water in areas where the local climatic conditions favour greenhouse production but limited supply of irrigation water constitutes a serious constraint.

Currently, CLS are not widely used in Mediterranean greenhouses, or in many other greenhouse systems around the world for several reasons,

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including the additional cost and the issue of salt accumulation (Incrocci et al., 2017; Giannothanas et al., 2024a). However, the most limiting factor that discourages the adoption of CLS is the complexity in managing plant nutrition in these cropping systems due to fluctuating nutrient concentrations in the recycled DS (Voogt and Bar-Yosef, 2019; Blok et al., 2023a). Fluctuating nutrient concentrations in the DS are mainly attributable to temporal variations in nutrient and water uptake by the plants caused by a diversity of factors, such as the genotype (cultivar), variations in climate conditions and fruit load, etc. (Neto et al., 2014; Ahn and Son, 2019; Blok et al., 2023b; Cedeño et al., 2023). Within a time interval in each crop, different combinations of these factors induce temporal fluctuations in uptake rates of individual nutrients which subsequently affect mutual uptake ratios. Because of these inevitable fluctuations in nutrient uptake rates, the supply of a nutrient

solution with standard concentrations in CLS cannot constantly maintain optimal target nutrient concentrations in the root solution (RS) (Kim et al., 2017). The net nutrient supply, i.e. the water and nutrients that are mixed with DS in a CLS, corresponds to the composition of a nutrient solution termed added solution (AS) (Blok et al., 2023a). The AS is mixed with recycled DS to form the nutrient solution supplied to the crop; hereafter, referred to as the supplied solution (SS) (Blok et al., 2023b; Savvas et al., 2024). A schematic representation of this concept is shown in Fig. 1A.

Currently, the management of nutrient composition in CLS uses regular (weekly, or bi-weekly) laboratory analysis of the DS with subsequent readjustment of the AS based on these analyses (Blok et al., 2023b). Nearly 30 % of the SS in CLS originates from the DS (Blok et al., 2023a). Thus, as the composition of one component of the SS, i.e., the DS

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of the nutrient solution and data flow in the two different treatments. Solid lines indicate nutrient solution or water flow. Dotted lines indicate information flow.

is variable, the intended concentrations in the SS cannot be constantly maintained. Frequent laboratory analyses of the DS have the objective of alleviating this issue. However, the time required to receive the analytical results in commercial practice ranges commonly from 4 to 7 days. Therefore, once the results are available, the composition of the DS may have changed appreciably since the samples were collected. The uncertainty in the composition of the DS creates inevitable inaccuracies in the calculation of a readjusted composition for the AS, that can be appreciable. Therefore, with the current technology used in commercial soilless greenhouses, optimal and balanced plant nutrition in CLS cannot be assured. Consequently, many greenhouse growers prefer to cultivate either in the soil or in open hydroponic systems if they are not forced by legislation to adopt CLS in soilless systems (Van der Salm et al., 2020; Peña-Fleitas et al., 2021).

A breakthrough in the current situation of uncertainty of the composition of the DS would be *in-situ* determination of the DS composition using ion selective electrodes (ISE). ISE are sensors capable of selectively estimating the concentration of a single ion in a multi-ion solution, such as a nutrient solution. ISE provide several advantages including very rapid and direct measurement, simplicity of use, wide measurement range, and no requirement to add reagents as is the case with colorimetric and refractometric methods (Cho et al., 2019; Padilla et al., 2020). In this regard, ISEs represent a promising tool for the daily monitoring of DS composition in combination with electrical conductivity (EC) and pH meters.

In recent years, numerous publications have presented ISE systems for soilless culture, including portable, manual, and automated options, which claim acceptable accuracy (Cho et al., 2019; Chowdhury et al., 2020; Han et al., 2020; Kim et al., 2017; Peña-Fleitas et al., 2021). Nevertheless, to date the use of ISEs remains at an experimental level and has hardly been adopted in commercial soilless CLS, as their long-term performance under greenhouse conditions needs further improvements (Han et al., 2020; Wu et al., 2023). A further limiting factor for the use of ISEs in commercial CLS is the lack of an integrated system for commercial farming, that comprises (i) ISEs, (ii) suitable software to readjust the net nutrient supply rates after receiving input from the ISEs, and (iii) suitable fertigation equipment to rapidly adjust and apply the modified nutrient supply. There has been considerable recent progress in the development of practical ISEs for on-farm measurement. ISEs for the reliable measurement of various macronutrients (e.g. NO_3^- , K^+ , Ca^{2+}) and other agriculturally important ions (e.g. Na^+) are now available (Peña-Fleitas et al., 2021, 2022).

An important factor limiting the use of ISE in soilless culture is the lack of a specialised technology (models, algorithms) to accurately calculate the injection rates for each nutrient as function of the ISE measurements, and to automatically adjust these rates. Currently, the standard technology used in greenhouses for the preparation and supply of nutrient solution to soilless crops is based on automated fertigation systems comprising two stock solutions of fertilisers and one stock solution of acid for pH adjustment (Van Os et al., 2019; Wu et al., 2023). With this technology, the mutual ratios of nutrients are fixed for as long as the two stock solutions are used; therefore, regular (e.g., daily) readjustments of the nutrient supply in response to ISE measurements are not feasible. Consequently, the introduction of ISE into commercial practice for precise optimal nutrient management in CLS requires a new generation of fertigation systems with multiple concentrated solutions of individual fertilisers. Additionally, developments in the software and electronics controlling the operation of such fertigation systems are required.

Considering these requirements, a system was developed and tested in a greenhouse tomato crop grown in a CLS that aimed to maintain optimal nutrient concentrations in the RS by daily readjusting the composition of the SS. In substrate-based soilless cropping systems, the nutrient concentrations in the RS are usually monitored by measurements in the DS. Sampling of the RS is technically more difficult (Blok et al., 2023a), and the composition of the DS and RS are similar as the

latter originates directly from the former (Voogt and Bar-Yosef, 2019). Therefore, in the current study, the two solutions will often be referred to collectively as RS/DS. The readjustment of the SS was based on daily *in situ* monitoring of nutrient concentrations in the DS using a set of ISE. The concentrations measured by the ISE were entered as input data to software within the DSS NUTRISENSE (Savvas et al., 2023; Giannothanasis et al., 2024a). This DSS was used to automatically calculate the injection rates of single fertiliser stock solutions. The output of NUTRISENSE was transmitted on-line to a fertigation system equipped with nine single-fertiliser concentrated solutions. The subsequent adjustments to nutrient concentrations in the SS were made in real time. In the current paper, the models and algorithms used by NUTRISENSE to daily readjust the nutrient supply in the CLS are presented, and the results from their experimental application in a greenhouse tomato crop are reported.

2. Model outline

2.1. System background

The system developed and tested in the current study aims to maintain optimal macronutrient concentrations in the RS. The RS was monitored by measuring the nutrient concentrations in the DS. The overall concept includes the following steps (Fig. 1B): i) daily measurement of macro-nutrient concentrations in the root zone of the plants using ISE; ii) on-line transmission or off-line introduction of measurements to the NUTRISENSE DSS which automatically calculates optimal EC, pH, and injection rates of nine single-fertiliser concentrated solutions to be applied on that day; iii) automated online transmission of the output of NUTRISENSE to a fertigation system equipped with nine single-fertiliser concentrated solutions, and iv) automated injection of the single-fertiliser concentrated solutions to a mix of irrigation water and DS, thereby obtaining the SS. Irrigation water and DS are mixed using a mixing device with an automatically adjustable mixing ratio of water to DS (Blok et al., 2023b). The water to DS mixing ratio is determined by the drainage fraction a ($a = 0-1$) in the mix, which can either be automatically measured as drainage to total supply fraction or introduced to the controlling system as a preset value. The micronutrient concentrations were not considered in the current study, because to date there are no reliable ISEs for their determination (Sambo et al., 2019).

2.2. Daily determination of the macro-ion concentrations in the DS

Sets of ISE for *in situ* determination of K^+ , Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , NH_4^+ , Na^+ , NO_3^- , P, and Cl^- in the greenhouse are available, and several studies have reported their use for the estimation of nutrient solution compositions (Cho et al., 2019; Chowdhury et al., 2020; Han et al., 2020; Kim et al., 2017; Peña-Fleitas et al., 2021). However, to date their robustness for long-term use under greenhouse conditions has not been proved, and their use in commercial applications is scarce.

In the current study, a set of four LAQUAtwin ISE (Horiba, Kyoto, Japan) were used to measure $[\text{K}^+]$, $[\text{Ca}^{2+}]$, $[\text{Na}^+]$ and $[\text{NO}_3^-]$ in the DS. LAQUAtwin electrodes are available only for these four macro ions. They cannot be connected online to the system to automatically measure nutrient concentrations. Measurements were made manually, and results were introduced to the NUTRISENSE software at a standard time every day. These ISE sensors were selected because in preliminary tests they proved to be very accurate and reliable, unlike some of the other ISE examined (Giannothanasis et al., 2024b).

Additionally, EC and pH were also measured directly in the DS using suitable portable instruments. The measured EC (E , dS m^{-1}) was substituted to Equation (1) as suggested by Sonneveld et al. (1999):

$$E = 0.1 \sum C_i^+ \quad (1)$$

to determine the total cation concentration ($\sum C_i^+$, meq L^{-1}) in the DS

after solving for $\sum C_i^+$.

The NH_4^+ concentration $[\text{NH}_4^+]$ in the DS is generally very low, being approximately 0–0.2 mM if the pH in the DS is inside the target range (5.5–6.5), because of nitrification and preferential uptake over NO_3^- -N (Sonneveld and Voogt, 2009; Savvas and Gruda, 2018). Therefore, the $[\text{NH}_4^+]$ in the DS can be considered negligible. Consequently, of the macronutrient cations, only $[\text{Mg}^{2+}]$ had to be indirectly estimated.

In a DS, the sums of the equivalent cation and anion concentrations ($\sum C_i^+$ and $\sum C_i^-$ in meq L^{-1} , respectively) are estimated as functions of the molar concentrations of each macro-ion ($[\cdot]$, mM).

$$\sum C_i^+ = [\text{K}^+] + 2 \cdot [\text{Ca}^{2+}] + 2 \cdot [\text{Mg}^{2+}] + [\text{Na}^+] + [\text{NH}_4^+] \quad (2)$$

$$\sum C_i^- = [\text{NO}_3^-] + [\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4^-] + 2 \cdot [\text{SO}_4^{2-}] + [\text{Cl}^-] + [\text{HCO}_3^-] \quad (3)$$

Furthermore, due to the cation-anion balance:

$$\sum C_i^+ = \sum C_i^- \quad (4)$$

Micronutrient cations and anions are neglected in (3) and (4), as their concentrations are much lower than those of macronutrients and, therefore, they do not have any impact on the anion to cation balance.

Equation (2) can be used to estimate the $[\text{Mg}^{2+}]$ in the DS after solving for $[\text{Mg}^{2+}]$. With respect to the anions, only $[\text{NO}_3^-]$ was measured with the LAQUAtwin electrodes. The concentration of $[\text{Cl}^-]$ was considered equal to that of $[\text{Na}^+]$, which is generally true if no Cl fertilisers are used for the preparation of nutrient solutions (Savvas et al., 2005; Varlagas et al., 2010; Giannothanasis et al., 2024a). The HCO_3^- concentration is very low (0.1–1.0 mM) in the DS if the pH is inside the target range of 5.5–6.5 (Savvas and Adamidis, 1999, 2000), and thus an average value for HCO_3^- within that range was used. The P concentration in the DS, which is mostly much lower than that of $[\text{NO}_3^-]$ by a factor of about 1:10 (Sonneveld and Voogt, 2009), was considered constant and equal to the target P concentration for the particular crop species. Finally, the sulphate concentration in the DS was calculated using (3) after solving for $[\text{SO}_4^{2-}]$.

2.3. Readjusting the composition of the supplied solution (SS)

NUTRISSENSE includes a database with standard target nutrient concentrations for each of the i macronutrients ($i = [\text{K}^+]$, $[\text{Ca}^{2+}]$, $[\text{Mg}^{2+}]$, $[\text{NH}_4^+]$, $[\text{NO}_3^-]$, $[\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4^-]$, and $[\text{SO}_4^{2-}]$) in the SS (C_{st}) and in the DS (C_{dt}) for a wide range of greenhouse-grown crops based on several literature sources (e.g., de Kreijl et al., 1999; Sonneveld and Voogt, 2009; Savvas et al., 2013; Van der Lugt et al., 2020). When a cultivated plant species is selected by the user of NUTRISSENSE, the C_{st} and the C_{dt} are available as starting values for each macronutrient. However, the actual concentration of the i macronutrient in the DS (C_{da}), as directly measured with the ISE or indirectly estimated using Equations (1)–(4), may be lower or higher than the C_{dt} values in the NUTRISSENSE database. In that case, the C_{st} values for the respective i nutrient are readjusted, i.e., they are increased or decreased, respectively, based on a mass balance model that aims to reestablish the target concentrations in the DS, i.e., to change these from C_{da} to C_{dt} . This model is presented below.

Based on a mass balance approach, the total mass (mmol per plant) of the i nutrient (M_i) that has to be added to or deducted from the sum of RS and DS to re-establish the target concentration (C_{dt}) in it can be estimated using the following equation (Savvas et al., 2023):

$$M_i = (C_{dt} - C_{da})V_d \quad (5)$$

where V_d is the total volume (L) of the sum of RS and DS per plant and C_{da} are the actual values measured by the ISE or estimated using the measured data. Depending on whether M_i has to be added to, or deducted from the standard supply, it can be a positive or a negative value.

Since M_i has to be added to, or deducted from the standard mass supplied to the crop via the SS, it will alter the concentration (mM) of the

i nutrient in the SS from the standard target value (C_{st}) to a new target value termed readjusted concentration (C_{sr}). The readjusted concentration is applied until the next readjustment. In the current study, readjustment of the macronutrient concentrations in the SS was taking place once per day (every morning) following introduction of the ISE measurements to NUTRISSENSE.

Based on a mass balance approach, M_i can be estimated also through the following equation:

$$M_i = V_s \Delta C_s \quad (6)$$

where V_s is the volume (L) of SS per plant per day and $\Delta C_s = C_{sr} - C_{st}$. Consequently, by combining Equations (5) and (6):

$$V_s \Delta C_s = (C_{dt} - C_{da})V_d \quad (7)$$

Rearranging Equation (7) and solving for ΔC_s renders:

$$\Delta C_s = \frac{(C_{dt} - C_{da})V_d}{V_s} \quad (8)$$

Finally, the readjusted nutrient concentration in the SS (C_{sr}) is calculated for each of the i macronutrients by adding ΔC_s to the target concentration in the SS (C_{st}).

$$C_{sr} = C_{st} + \Delta C_s \quad (9)$$

In CLS, the SS is prepared by injecting nutrients to the mix of DS and water. Therefore, the C_{sr} values estimated using Equation (9) are subject to the following physical constraint:

$$C_{sr} \geq aC_{da} + (1 - a)C_w \quad (10)$$

Furthermore, the readjusted target EC value (dS m^{-1}) in the final SS (E_{sr}) is calculated using the following Equation derived from Savvas and Adamidis (1999, 2000):

$$E_{sr} = \frac{C_{sr} + 1.462}{9.819}$$

In Equation (10), a is the target drainage fraction (0–1), and C_w is the concentration of this nutrient in the raw water used to prepare NS. A further constraint for the readjusted composition of the SS is the anion to cation balance which is taken into consideration by using mostly $[\text{SO}_4^{2-}]$ as counterbalancing ion.

According to the standard practice currently applied in commercial CLS, the DS is initially mixed with raw water at a ratio adjusted automatically to obtain a preset EC (E_m) in the mix (Blok et al., 2023b). Thus, NUTRISSENSE calculates the concentration of each macro ion in the mix of DS and water using the following equation:

$$C_m = aC_{da} + (1 - a)C_w \quad (11)$$

where a is the target drainage fraction (0–1), and C_w is the concentration of this nutrient in the raw water used to prepare NS. Subsequently, NUTRISSENSE calculates the sum of the equivalent macro cation concentrations in the mix of water and DS ($\sum C_{im}^+$) using Equation (2) after replacement of $[\text{K}^+]$, $[\text{Ca}^{2+}]$, $[\text{Mg}^{2+}]$, $[\text{NH}_4^+]$, $[\text{Na}^+]$ with the respective C_m values obtained from Equation (11). The next step is the calculation of a target EC for the mix of DS and water (E_m) using Equation (1) after replacement of E with E_m and C_i with $\sum C_{im}^+$. The estimated E_m is transmitted by NUTRISSENSE to the system controlling the mixing ratio between DS and water. Thus, the nutrient concentrations in the mix will be those estimated using Equation (11) when its EC is automatically adjusted to E_m .

The daily readjusted injection rate of each nutrient (C_{nr} , mM) to the mix of DS and water that is needed to achieve the readjusted concentration of this nutrient in the SS (C_{sr}) is calculated using the following equation:

$$C_{nr} = C_{sr} - C_m \quad (12)$$

Consequently, by substituting Equation (11) for C_m in Equation (12), the following equation is obtained:

$$C_{nr} = C_{sr} - aC_{da} - (1 - a)C_w \quad (13)$$

After these adaptations, the final C_{nr} values obtained from Equation (13) are transmitted to a series of algorithms described by Savvas and Adamidis (1999, 2000) which are part of NUTRISENSE, to estimate the injection rate of each individual fertiliser. The estimated injection rates are automatically transmitted by NUTRISENSE to an on-line connected fertigation system comprising nine single-fertiliser concentrated solutions (including one for acid injection). Subsequently, the single-fertiliser concentrated solutions are automatically injected to the mixture of DS and raw water at the calculated injection rates, which are different every day. This fertigation system with the 8 + 1 tanks of concentrated fertiliser solutions was specifically developed for use with ISEs to automatically modify daily the applied nutrient solution formula. This system is substantially different than the conventional two-tank systems (A and B) which operate with fixed injection ratios.

In the above algorithm, only Equation (1) is empirical, but its accuracy is sufficient for application in nutrient solutions applied in commercial soilless greenhouses (Sonneveld, 2002). All other Equations (2–13) are based on mass balance, while including either known or measured parameters and, thus, the accuracy of the estimated nutrient injection rates is expected to be high.

3. Materials and methods

3.1. Experimental design, plant material and growth conditions

To evaluate the efficiency of the models and algorithms described in Section 2 to maintain the target nutrient concentrations in the root zone of the plants, an experiment with tomato grown in two CLSs was carried out in a greenhouse of the Agricultural University of Athens (AUA: 37°58'54.2"N 23°42'22.0"E, altitude 35 m). Sixteen experimental plots were used, each of them corresponding to a 6-m long gutter. In each gutter, six bags (100 × 20 × 15 cm) were placed containing composted coconut fruit husk. Each bag accommodated 2 tomato plants at a density of 2.9 plants m⁻². The sixteen experimental plots were randomly allocated into two different treatments, with eight replications per treatment. In both treatments, the total volume of DS was collected in separate catchment tanks and recycled after addition of water and nutrients; therefore, both treatments were CLS.

Before planting, the coconut compost was moistened to the point of container capacity using a nutrient solution with a composition suggested by Sonneveld and Voogt (2009) as optimal for the root zone of soilless-grown tomato plants. Irrigation with a SS according to Sonneveld and Voogt (2009) for open soilless cropping systems started 11 days after transplanting (DAT). After a further 5 days, when sufficient DS was collected in the catchment tanks, recycling of the DS was initiated in both treatments.

In the first treatment, which served as a control, current standard practice of nutrient management in CLS was followed, with adjustment of the AS composition made every two weeks after a laboratory analysis of the DS as described by Giannothanasis et al. (2024b). The adjustment was performed using the DSS NUTRISENSE as described by Savvas et al. (2023). In the second treatment (ISE-NUTRISENSE treatment), the addition of K, Ca, Mg, NO₃⁻, and SO₄²⁻ was readjusted daily by using the new algorithm described in Subsection 2.3. Every day at 9.00 a.m., a composite representative sample of DS was collected, and the [K⁺], [Ca²⁺], [Na⁺] and [NO₃⁻] were measured using LAQUAtwin ISE sensors, models K-11, Ca-11, Na-11 and NO₃-11, respectively (Horiba, Kyoto, Japan). In the same DS samples, EC and pH were determined using suitable portable sensors (HI98312 and HI8424, respectively, Hanna Instr. Inc., Woonsocket RI, USA). The calibration points used for the LAQUAtwin ISE sensors are presented in Table 1. The concentrations of Mg²⁺, NH₄⁺, P, Cl⁻, HCO₃⁻ and SO₄²⁻ in the DS were estimated as

Table 1

Concentrations used as calibration points for the ISE of K⁺, Ca²⁺, NO₃⁻ and Na⁺ (LAQUAtwin, Horiba, Kyoto, Japan).

Nutrient	Low calibration point		High calibration point	
	mM	mg L ⁻¹	mM	mg L ⁻¹
K ⁺	3.84	150	15.35	600
Ca ²⁺	3.74	150	14.97	600
Na ⁺	0.65	15	6.52	150
NO ₃ ⁻	2.42	150	32.26	2000

described in Subsection 2.2. Subsequently, the above data were manually entered into the NUTRISENSE DSS, and the new composition of the SS was recalculated as described in Subsection 2.3. The micronutrient concentrations were monitored, and their supply rates were adjusted fortnightly based on standard laboratory analysis, as used for the DS in the control treatment.

The SS was prepared by a fertigation system (ALAGRO, Athens, Greece) equipped with nine tanks of concentrated fertiliser solutions. The fertilisers placed in each of the nine concentrated solution tanks were calcium nitrate, potassium nitrate, ammonium nitrate, monopotassium phosphate, potassium sulphate, magnesium nitrate, magnesium sulphate, iron chelate (Fe-EDDHA, 6 % Fe), and nitric acid. The concentrations of the fertilisers in the nine concentrated solution tanks were: calcium nitrate: 80 kg m⁻³, potassium nitrate: 100 kg m⁻³, ammonium nitrate: 20 kg m⁻³, magnesium nitrate: 40 kg m⁻³, magnesium sulphate: 40 kg m⁻³, potassium sulphate: 40 kg m⁻³, monopotassium phosphate: 50 kg m⁻³, and iron chelate: 3 kg m⁻³. The micronutrients Mn, Zn, Cu, B and Mo were added together to the stock solution of monopotassium phosphate. To prepare the SS, the fertigation system mixed the DS with raw water up to a target EC (E_m). The mineral composition of the raw water was as described in a previous study (Giannothanasis et al., 2024a). Subsequently, stock solutions of fertilisers were added up to the target EC for the SS (E_{sr}) at injection rates daily readjusted by NUTRISENSE after manual input of the ISE measurements. The E_{sr} was also readjusted every day by NUTRISENSE, together with the injection rates of fertiliser stock solutions. Following the daily recalculation of the SS composition, the NUTRISENSE DSS transmitted online the E_m , E_{sr} , and the injection rates of the nine fertiliser stock solutions to the fertigation system, which used this input to prepare the SS with the readjusted composition. The system comprising the four LAQUAtwin sensors, the NUTRISENSE DSS, and the multi-tank fertigation machinery that was connected online with NUTRISENSE, will be henceforth, referred to as the ISE-NUTRISENSE system.

Tomato seedlings (*Solanum lycopersicum* L. 'Ekstasis F1') were transplanted to the coconut slabs on October 26, 2023 which is considered as 0 DAT. The recycling of the DS was initiated at 16 DAT and the experiment was terminated on March 22, 2024 (at 148 DAT). Harvesting of fruits commenced on January 22, 2024 (88 DAT). The plants were pruned into a single stem which descended when the top of the stem reached the level of the supporting wires. Through weekly defoliation of old leaves from the bottom, 16 to 18 leaves were maintained on each plant, aiming at a leaf area index (LAI) of approximately 3 (Jun et al., 2020). In both treatments, the drainage fraction was maintained close to 0.35 by adjusting the frequency of irrigation with SS according to the climatic conditions.

3.2. Sampling and laboratory analysis

In the control treatment, the concentrations of all nutrients in the DS were determined eight times during the experiment, at 21, 39, 56, 72, 87, 102, 117, and 132 DAT by employing standard laboratory instruments. The data obtained were used to readjust the composition of the AS using NUTRISENSE (Savvas et al., 2023). On these dates, samples of DS were also collected from the ISE treatment and were used to determine the concentrations of all nutrients. However, in the ISE

treatment, only the P and micronutrient concentrations were readjusted in the AS on those dates using the data obtained from the laboratory measurements. In the ISE treatment, K^+ , Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , NO_3^- and SO_4^{2-} concentrations in the SS were readjusted daily using the ISE measurements. The measurements of $[K^+]$, $[Ca^{2+}]$, $[Mg^{2+}]$, $[NO_3^-]$, and $[SO_4^{2-}]$ in the DS by standard laboratory instruments at 21, 39, 56, 72, 87, 102, 117, and 132 DAT, were used only for comparison with the respective measurements of ISE in the same samples. The nutrients and non-nutrient ions measured in the laboratory at 21, 39, 56, 72, 87, 102, 117, and 132 DAT using standard analytical methods (Giannothanasis et al., 2024a) were K^+ , Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Na^+ , NO_3^- , SO_4^{2-} , P, Cl^- , HCO_3^- , Fe, Mn, Zn, Cu, and B.

Moreover, to calculate the harvest index, the total vegetative and fruit biomass of three randomly selected plants from each replicate plot were collected for the whole experimental period, including leaves and stems removed by pruning. Since the harvest index is calculated as the fraction of dry fruit biomass to total dried biological biomass (Shu et al., 2020), representative samples of both the vegetative and fruit biomass were dried at 65 °C to constant weight, whenever vegetative or fruit biomass was collected. To determine the fruit dry matter content, fruit samples were randomly selected from each experimental unit on each harvest date. Part of the fruit samples was used for fruit quality analysis, while the rest was weighed, then dried at 65 °C to constant weight, and weighed again.

At 35, 65, 95, 115 and 148 DAT, the fourth leaf from the top (Campbell, 2000; Sonneveld and Voogt, 2009) of six randomly selected plants was sampled at each replication to determine the leaf nutrient concentrations. The sampled leaves were cleaned using distilled water, dried at 65 °C to constant weight, powdered using a blade mill, and sieved through a 40-mesh sieve. Subsequently, the pulverised leaf samples were dry ashed at 550 °C and used to determine the concentrations of K, Ca and Mg, following their extraction with 1 M HCl (Campbell and Plank, 1997) and using an atomic absorption spectrophotometer (AA-7000, Shimadzu Corp., Japan). The total-N content was determined according to the Kjeldahl method, using a Labtec DT 220 digestion system and a Tecator Kjeltec 8200 titration system (FOSS A/S, Hillerod, Denmark).

Water productivity was calculated as the weight of fruit produced per volume of used water ($kg\ m^{-3}$) (Fernández et al., 2020; Pereira et al., 2012) and agronomic efficiency of N as kg of fruit produced per kg of supplied nitrogen ($kg\ kg^{-1}$) (Ladha et al., 2005). Total soluble solid content in the fruit samples collected for quality analysis was measured using a refractometer (Schmidt and Haensch HR32B, Berlin, Germany). Titratable acidity of the fruit samples was determined in 10 mL of fruit juice by potentiometric titration with 0.02 M NaOH to pH 8.1. The taste index was calculated as proposed by Navez et al. (1999) and Nielsen (2003) using the following equation:

$$Taste\ index = \frac{Brix\ degree}{20 \times acidity} + acidity$$

3.3. Statistical analyses

The experiment was set up as a completely randomized design with two treatments and eight replications per treatment. The significance of the differences between treatments was assessed by applying one-way ANOVA. The statistical analysis of the data, ANOVA and linear regressions were performed using the STATISTICA 12.5 for Windows (StatSoft Inc., Tulsa, USA). The graphical representation of data was carried out using the GraphPad Prism 8 software (GraphPad Software, USA).

4. Results

4.1. Evolution of macronutrient concentrations in the root-drainage solution

Fig. 2 illustrates the evolution of EC, Na^+ , and macronutrient concentrations in the DS of both treatments during the whole experimental period. In both CLSs, the EC in the DS was maintained very close to the target of $4\ dS\ m^{-1}$ throughout the experimental period, with deviations within the range of $\pm 5\%$ (Fig. 2A). A significant difference between the treatments was observed only at 56 DAT, when the EC was closer to the target level in the ISE-NUTRISENSE treatment than in the control. The $[NO_3^-]$ in the DS was lower than the target level on the first sampling date (21 DAT) but increased thereafter and closely approached the target level in both treatments on the next sampling dates (Fig. 2B). Significant differences between the two treatments were observed at 56, 72, 102 and 148 DAT, with $[NO_3^-]$ being closer to the target concentration in the ISE-NUTRISENSE treatment than in the control on all these sampling dates. Initially, in both treatments the $[K^+]$ in the DS (Fig. 2C) was approximately 50 % higher than the target value (21 DAT). Subsequently, for the rest of the cropping period, the $[K^+]$ in the ISE treatment was maintained close to the target value, while in the control it exhibited notable deviations, with significant differences from the ISE at 39, 56, 72, 87, 102, 117 and 148 DAT. The $[Ca^{2+}]$ and $[Mg^{2+}]$ in DS also exhibited larger deviations from the target value in the control than in the ISE-NUTRISENSE treatment, with significant differences at five and four sampling dates, respectively (Fig. 2D and E). The $[Na^+]$ in the DS (Fig. 2F) remained almost stable ranging from 3.5 to 4.7 mM without any significant differences between the two treatments.

4.2. Evolution of mutual ratios between macronutrients in the root-drainage solution

Fig. 3 illustrates the evolution of some important molar ratios between pairs of macronutrients in the DS (K:N, K:Ca, K:Mg), where the actual ratios are compared with the target ratios derived from standard literature sources (Sonneveld and Voogt, 2009). In the ISE-NUTRISENSE treatment, the molar K:N ratio was maintained close to the target (4.1), with less than 10 % deviation from the target value except for the first sampling day; the corresponding discrepancies from the target in the control were higher than 30 % on 72, 102, 117 and 148 DAT. In the ISE-NUTRISENSE treatment, the molar K:Ca ratio in the DS was stable with a maximum deviation of $\pm 5\%$ from the target value (0.80) after the initial sampling day (21 DAT), while in the control the discrepancies were much larger. Significant differences between the two treatments in the K:Ca ratio were observed at 39, 72, 87, 102, 117 and 148 DAT (Fig. 3B). The molar K:Mg ratio in the ISE-NUTRISENSE treatment was substantially closer to the target level (1.8) compared to the control on all sampling dates except for 132 DAT (Fig. 3C). Significant differences between the two treatments were observed on 72, 102, 117, 132 and 148 DAT.

4.3. Daily measurements with ion selective electrodes

Fig. 4 presents the daily measurements of $[NO_3^-]$, $[K^+]$, $[Ca^{2+}]$, and $[Na^+]$ in the DS using both ISE instruments and standard laboratory procedures. After an initial phase of gradual convergence, most measurements of $[NO_3^-]$, $[K^+]$, and $[Ca^{2+}]$ were within the range of $\pm 10\%$ deviation from the target values in the DS. The values obtained from the ISEs measurements were in close agreement with those obtained by laboratory instruments for $[NO_3^-]$, $[K^+]$, $[Ca^{2+}]$, and $[Na^+]$. Furthermore, as shown in Fig. 5, the linear regressions between the ISE measurements and those obtained using standard laboratory instruments for $[NO_3^-]$, $[K^+]$, $[Ca^{2+}]$, and $[Na^+]$ were very close to the 1:1 line, as indicated by slope values of 1.017, 1.022, 1.006, and 0.997, respectively. The corresponding intercept values, signifying the zero relative

Fig. 2. Evolution of EC, $[\text{NO}_3^-]$, $[\text{K}^+]$, $[\text{Ca}^{2+}]$, $[\text{Mg}^{2+}]$ and $[\text{Na}^+]$ in drainage solution (DS) samples collected approx. every fortnight from the two treatments during the experiment. The horizontal dotted lines show the standard target value of EC, $[\text{NO}_3^-]$, $[\text{K}^+]$, $[\text{Ca}^{2+}]$ and $[\text{Mg}^{2+}]$ in the DS. Vertical bars denote \pm standard errors of means ($n = 8$), while *, **, and *** indicate significant differences according to ANOVA test ($p < 0.05$) at $p < 0.05$, $p < 0.01$, and $p < 0.001$, respectively.

error, were 0.4271, 0.1534, 0.2140, and 0.001 for $[\text{NO}_3^-]$, $[\text{K}^+]$, $[\text{Ca}^{2+}]$, and $[\text{Na}^+]$, respectively.

Fig. 6 shows the $[\text{Mg}^{2+}]$ concentrations estimated: i) daily by NUTRISENSE using Equations (1) and (2) after introducing the daily measurements of the EC-meter for EC and of the ISE for K^+ , Ca^{2+} , and Na^+ , as detailed in Section 2.2, and ii) in the laboratory by employing standard instruments and procedures. Compared with the measurements of the other four macronutrients obtained using ISE, the estimated $[\text{Mg}^{2+}]$ exhibited larger deviations from the values measured in the same samples using standard laboratory instruments. Furthermore, compared to the $[\text{NO}_3^-]$, $[\text{K}^+]$, $[\text{Ca}^{2+}]$ measured with ISE, the estimated $[\text{Mg}^{2+}]$ values in the DS exhibited larger deviations from the target value, and exceeded more frequently the range of $\pm 10\%$ deviation.

4.4. Leaf nutrient concentrations

In Fig. 7, the leaf concentrations of N, K, Ca and Mg measured at five sampling dates in the fourth leaf of the tomato plants are presented. The total-N (Fig. 7A) was similar in both treatments during the first three sampling dates, but at 120 and 148 DAT it was significantly higher in the ISE-NUTRISENSE treatment than in the control (49.1 vs. 45.8, and 49.5 vs. 46.8 mg g^{-1} , respectively). Potassium exhibited a declining trend in

the control during the cultivation period, while in the ISE-NUTRISENSE treatment it did not change significantly (Fig. 7B). At 95, 120 and 148 DAT, the leaf K in the ISE-NUTRISENSE treatment was 50.0, 49.5 and 38.4 mg g^{-1} , respectively, while in the control it decreased significantly to 45.3, 43.0 and 28.0 mg g^{-1} , respectively. The leaf Ca and Mg concentrations were similar in the two treatments during the initial 120 days, but on the last sampling day (148 DAT) both Ca and Mg decreased to significantly lower levels in the control than in the ISE-NUTRISENSE treatment (Fig. 7C and D).

4.5. Yield, fruit quality, harvest index, water and nitrogen use

The control treatment produced 16.74 kg m^{-2} of tomato fruit, while the adjustment of macronutrient supply using ISE to daily measure $[\text{NO}_3^-]$, $[\text{K}^+]$, $[\text{Ca}^{2+}]$, and $[\text{Na}^+]$ in the DS increased the yield to 18.01 kg m^{-2} , which corresponds to a 7.6 % enhancement of production (Table 2). This difference is attributed to a 7.9 % increase in the number of fruits per plant, while the mean fruit weight was not affected by the treatments (Table 2). Furthermore, a 6.8 % rise in total soluble solids content was observed in the fruits of the ISE-NUTRISENSE treatment, compared to the control while the titratable acidity, the fruit dry matter content and the taste index remained unaffected (Table 2). It is

Fig. 3. Evolution of the ratios between $[K^+]$ and the $[NO_3^-]$, $[Ca^{2+}]$ and $[Mg^{2+}]$ in drainage solution (DS) samples collected approx. every fortnight from the two treatments during the experiment. The horizontal dotted lines show the standard target value of each ratio. Vertical bars denote \pm standard errors of means ($n = 8$), while *, **, and *** indicate significant differences according to ANOVA test ($p < 0.05$) at $p < 0.05$, $p < 0.01$, and $p < 0.001$, respectively.

noteworthy that the ISE strategy increased significantly the harvest index of the plants by 12.8 %, i.e., to 0.53 from 0.47 in the control (Table 3). Concomitantly, water productivity was improved by 7.6 %, when ISE were used to control the DS recycling, i.e., from 26.5 in the control to 28.5 $kg\ m^{-3}$ in the ISE-NUTRISENSE treatment. Furthermore, a 23 % higher agronomic efficiency of N was also achieved in the ISE treatment compared to the control (Table 3).

5. Discussion

The effectiveness of nutrient management strategies in soilless cropping systems depends mainly on their ability to maintain the target nutrient concentrations in the root zone (Blok et al., 2023b; Sonneveld and Voogt, 2009; Voogt and Bar-Yosef, 2019). However, due to the low rooting volume and the low buffering capacity in soilless culture, the nutrient concentrations in the RS/DS can rapidly change resulting in nutrient imbalances. The risk of nutrient imbalances is more serious in CLS because the DS contributes by about 30 % to the total volume of the SS, and thus it can modify its composition in an unpredictable manner (Savvas and Gruda, 2018). To address this problem, many investigators have pointed to ISEs as means to monitor the nutrient concentrations in the root zone of the plants (e.g., Bamsey et al., 2012; Savvas et al., 2021, 2023b; Cho et al., 2018, 2023; Wu et al., 2023). However, there are three prerequisites to successfully apply ISEs for the control of nutrient supply in CLS. The first prerequisite is the availability of robust and accurate ISEs of as many as possible nutrients for long-term *in-situ* use in greenhouses. The second prerequisite is the use of a suitable software to automatically process the ISE measurements and provide a modified SS formula, capable of re-establishing the target nutrient concentrations in the RS/DS. The third prerequisite is the use of suitable equipment, i.e., a specialised fertigation system, to automatically apply a modified SS formula whenever transmitted on-line from the software.

Several investigators developed and/or tested ISEs focusing of the accuracy of their measurements under different conditions (e.g., Rius-Ruiz et al., 2014; Kim et al., 2013, 2017; Cho et al., 2018; Wu et al., 2023), and the factors influencing their performance (Han et al., 2020; Silva-Pumarada and Di Gioia, 2023). Furthermore, several software approaches based on two-point calibration (Chowdhury et al., 2020) and neural networks (Cho et al., 2019) have been developed to overcome measurement errors, optimise calibration of ISEs, and maximise the accuracy of the data provided by ISEs (Tuan et al., 2020; Wu et al., 2023). However, there are few, if any, reports addressing the second and third prerequisites for successful use of ISEs in CLS. The current study is the first report on successful implementation of ISEs in a long-term soilless tomato crop under semi-commercial greenhouse conditions using a special DSS to control the nutrient input based on the ISE measurements. A decision-tree based dosing algorithm to calculate optimal volumes of individual nutrient stock solutions based on feedback by ISE has been developed also by Cho et al. (2023) who used dosing pumps to implement the output of the algorithm. However, their approach was based on successive calculation of masses ($mg\ L^{-1}$) of the required nutrients and fertilisers, ignoring the anion to cation balance and the electrochemical constraints governing the composition of multi-salt solutions. As a result, over-injection of NO_3^- was observed (Cho et al., 2023). Taking into consideration the electrochemical complexity of the nutrient solutions is essential to avoid over- or under-injection of nutrients, especially when some nutrient concentrations in the DS differ substantially from target levels, a situation that is more likely to occur in long-term crops. The algorithm used in the current study is fully based on achieving anion to cation balance and respecting the electrochemical equilibria, while considering all nutrient ions and fertilisers simultaneously based on a holistic approach. Similar approaches based on ion balance and electrochemical equilibria have been applied also by Savvas and Adamidis (1999, 2000) and de Kreij et al. (1999) to establish nutrient recommendation systems for soilless culture systems as defined by Blok et al. (2023a).

Fig. 4. Daily course of $[NO_3^-]$, $[K^+]$, $[Ca^{2+}]$, and $[Na^+]$ in DS samples collected from the ISE treatment and measured with both ISE and standard laboratory procedures. The horizontal dotted lines delimit the $\pm 10\%$ range from the target level.

Fig. 5. Linear regression between the $[NO_3^-]$, $[K^+]$, $[Ca^{2+}]$, and $[Na^+]$ in the DS measured daily in the greenhouse with ISE and those determined in the laboratory applying standard methodologies. The dotted line denotes the 1:1 line, while the solid line represents the fitted equation.

Fig. 6. Daily course of $[Mg^{2+}]$ in DS samples collected from the ISE treatment as estimated: i) automatically by NUTRISENSE using the $[NO_3^-]$, $[K^+]$, $[Ca^{2+}]$, and $[Na^+]$ measurements with ISE, and the EC measured with a portable EC-meter, and ii) by applying standard laboratory procedures. The horizontal dotted lines delimit the $\pm 10\%$ range from the target level.

Although the current study was commissioned to develop and validate a DSS and a specialised fertigation system for optimal utilisation of ISE measurements and not to validate ISE performance, the accuracy of the ISEs used in the current study was assessed. The results clearly demonstrated the effectiveness of the ISEs, when combined with suitable software, to maintain the DS composition close to the targets (Fig. 2). The accuracy of the LAQUAtwin ISEs have been shown in previous studies and were confirmed in the current study (Figs. 4 and 5). Peña-Fleitas et al. (2021) used the NO_3^- sensor for measurements in NS, soil solution and petiole sap samples and reported very good agreement between ISE measurements and those obtained with standard laboratory equipment. The LAQUAtwin NO_3^- sensor delivered similar results when measuring NO_3^- in hydroponic NSs (Silva-Pumarada and Di Gioia, 2023) or soil solution samples (Cabrera Corral et al., 2016). Cabrera Corral et al. (2016) compared the K^+ concentrations measured with a LAQUAtwin sensor in soil samples with those obtained with standards

analytical methods in the laboratory and found a good fit to the 1:1 line with a slope value of 0.99 and an R^2 of 0.88. Furthermore, Cabrera Corral et al. (2016) tested the LAQUAtwin Na^+ sensor in soil solution samples and found a high accuracy with a slope value of 1.06. However, in the same study, the LAQUAtwin sensor for Ca^{2+} showed an overestimation, as indicated by an intercept value of $+1.75$ mM. When using ISE systems, care must be taken to ensure their correct operation. Appropriate procedures are described in Mikhelson (2013), Cho et al. (2018) and Peña-Fleitas et al. (2021). Particular care should be taken with sample temperature. For the LAQUAtwin NO_3^- system, measurements are sensitive to sample temperature (Peña-Fleitas et al., 2022). Temperature effects were minimal at 17–22 °C; below there is an overestimation, and above an underestimation (Peña-Fleitas et al., 2022). Cooled samples are particularly sensitive, the errors being $+50\%$ at 5 °C and $+31\%$ at 10 °C. These temperature limitations were considered in the measurements performed with the LAQUAtwin electrodes in the current study.

In the current study, the deviation between the estimated $[Mg^{2+}]$ in the RS/DS and those measured with standard laboratory procedures in the same samples were larger than the corresponding deviations of $[K^+]$, $[Ca^{2+}]$, and $[Na^+]$. However, the $[K^+]$, $[Ca^{2+}]$ and $[Na^+]$ concentrations were measured with both ISEs and standard laboratory procedures, while $[Mg^{2+}]$ was not measured with ISEs but estimated as a function of the $[K^+]$, $[Ca^{2+}]$, $[Na^+]$ and EC measurements using Equation (2). Consequently, the small measurement errors of $[K^+]$, $[Ca^{2+}]$, $[Na^+]$ and EC using ISEs were additive in the estimated $[Mg^{2+}]$. Nevertheless, the accuracy of the estimated $[Mg^{2+}]$ in the DS based on the ISE measurements of $[K^+]$, $[Ca^{2+}]$, $[Na^+]$, as well as on that of EC, was sufficient for long-term maintenance of its concentration in the RS/DS close to the target values.

As shown in Figs. 3 and 4, the concentrations of all macronutrients measured or estimated in the DS (K^+ , Ca^{2+} , NO_3^- , Mg^{2+}) deviated substantially from the target levels during the first three weeks in both treatments but thereafter gradually shifted towards to the target values. These initial discrepancies from the target values were due to the use of coconut compost as growing media, which is known to include

Fig. 7. Evolution of total-N, $[K^+]$, $[Ca^{2+}]$, and $[Mg^{2+}]$ in the fourth leaf of tomato plants on five sampling dates during the experimental period. The concentrations are presented as $mg\ g^{-1}$ in dry biomass. Vertical bars denote \pm standard errors of means ($n = 8$), while *, **, and *** indicate significant differences according to ANOVA test ($p < 0.05$) at $p < 0.05$, $p < 0.01$, and $p < 0.001$, respectively.

Table 2

Yield per m², mean fruit weight, number of fruits per plant, total soluble solids expressed as °Brix, titratable acidity expressed as % citric acid, fruit dry matter content (%) and taste index in the two treatments.

Parameter	Control treatment	ISE treatment	Relative difference (%)	Statistical significance
Yield (Kg m ⁻²)	16.74	18.01	7.6	**
Mean fruit weight (g)	270.9	269.0		NS
Number of fruits per plant	21.4	23.1	7.9	*
Total soluble solids content (°Brix)	4.56	4.87	6.8	*
Titratable acidity (Citric acid % (w/w))	0.41	0.42		NS
Fruit dry matter content (%)	4.8	4.7		NS
Taste index	0.97	1.00		NS

In each row, means (n = 8) of the two treatments are presented. Statistical differences according to ANOVA test are denoted by NS for not significant, while *, **, and *** indicate significance at p ≤ 0.05, p ≤ 0.01, and p ≤ 0.001, respectively.

Table 3

Harvest index as the dry yield biomass divided by the total dried biological biomass, water productivity as weight of fruit produced per volume of water consumed (kg m⁻³), and agronomic efficiency of N as kg of fruit produced per kg of supplied nitrogen (kg kg⁻¹).

Parameter	Control treatment	ISE treatment	Relative difference (%)	Statistical significance
Harvest index	0.47	0.53	12.8	**
water productivity (kg m ⁻³)	26.5	28.5	7.6	**
Agronomic efficiency of N (kg kg ⁻¹)	140.0	172.2	23.0	***

In each row, means (n = 8) of the two treatments are presented. Statistical differences according to ANOVA test are denoted by NS for not significant, while *, **, and *** indicate significance at p ≤ 0.05, p ≤ 0.01, and p ≤ 0.001, respectively.

substantial amounts of exchangeable K⁺, but gradually this is replaced by Ca²⁺ when a nutrient solution is supplied, until an equilibrium is established (Handreck, 1993; Shinohara et al., 1999; Xiong et al., 2017). Coconut compost is a chemically active substrate (Raviv et al., 2002) and, therefore, typically the composition of the RS of plants grown on this substrate is subjected to appreciable changes due to ion exchange processes during the initial phase of crop growth. The ISE-NUTRISENSE system needed some days to restore the target concentrations in the RS because, after transplanting, the plants were very small and thus their daily needs for SS were very low. Consequently, the small volume of RS supplied daily to the plants at that stage was unable to impose the necessary changes in the composition of the RS.

The use of the ISE-NUTRISENSE system to automatically readjust every day the supply rates of macronutrients according to the ISE measurements successfully maintained the nutrient concentrations in the RS/DS close to the target values. Overall, the daily measured macronutrient concentrations in the DS exhibited smaller deviations from the target values in the ISE-NUTRISENSE system than in the control. Hence, the ISE-NUTRISENSE system improved the nutrient status in the root zone of the plants compared to the current practice which is based on fertigation systems with 2 + 1 concentrated solutions and bi-weekly modification of their composition after laboratory analysis of the DS. Apart from the target concentrations of each individual nutrient,

their mutual ratios in the DS play an important role and are widely used for nutrient management in soilless culture (Fanasca et al., 2006; Voogt and Bar-Yosef, 2019; Ahn et al., 2021). In the current study, the K:NO₃, K:Ca and K:Mg ratios in the DS/RS were maintained close to the target values in the ISE-NUTRISENSE treatment. However, in the control treatment the larger fluctuations in [K⁺], [Ca²⁺], and [Mg²⁺] from the target concentrations resulted in substantial deviations in the mutual macrocation ratios, even though the EC remained relatively stable. In a previous study, Giannothanasis et al. (2024a) found that keeping the mutual ratios of nutrients in the RS close to the target values ensured optimal plant nutrition even if the absolute concentrations were lower than the corresponding target values.

Given that nutrient shortages result in irrevocable damage after 1.5–7 days (Marcelis et al., 2003; Blok et al., 2023a), it is reasonable to anticipate benefits for plant growth and fruit production due to the use of the ISE-NUTRISENSE system to control plant nutrition in CLS. Indeed, tomato fruit yield was 7.6 % higher in the ISE-NUTRISENSE treatment compared to the control. The larger deviations of [K⁺], [Ca²⁺], [Mg²⁺] and [NO₃⁻] from the target levels in the DS/RS of the control compared to the ISE-NUTRISENSE treatment did not cause nutrient deficiencies or toxicities. However, as pointed out by Blok et al. (2023a), plants are capable of tailoring nutrient uptake rates to their nutrient requirements by spending metabolic energy. The larger are the deviations of the actual concentrations and mutual nutrient ratios in the RS from the corresponding target values, the higher is the energy consumption by the plants (Poorter et al., 1991; Alborno and Lieth, 2017), so long as the higher energy cost can meet the plant demand for nutrients (Blok et al., 2017). However, the higher energy consumption required to maintain optimal uptake ratios between nutrients despite their deviations in the RS has a cost in plant growth and fruit production (Rewald et al., 2016).

The K:N ratio in the RS also has an impact on yield parameters in tomato, mainly by influencing the balance between vegetative and reproductive growth (Heuvelink, 2018). In the current study, the more efficient maintenance of the K:N ratio in the RS close to the target value with the ISE-NUTRISENSE system may have also contributed to the higher number of fruits per plant and the significant increase of the harvest index in this treatment compared to the control treatment. The higher fruit yield may partly be due to increased allocation of plant assimilates to fruit in the ISE-NUTRISENSE treatment compared to the control. The increase in water productivity is due to the higher total yield in the ISE-NUTRISENSE treatment, as the water supply was similar in both treatments. The water productivity achieved in the ISE-NUTRISENSE treatment is higher than those reported from other studies with CLS, highlighting the environmental aspect of improving yield performance in CLS, as also suggested by Santamaria et al. (2003), Valenzano et al. (2008) and Ullah et al. (2021). However, the agronomic efficiency of N increased appreciably more than the yield in the ISE-NUTRISENSE treatment compared with the control, indicating that the overall improvement of the nutrient status in the root zone of the plants in the former resulted in an overall lower N input to the system. The agronomic efficiency of N in the control treatment of the current study agrees with the results of Giannothanasis et al. (2024a) in a tomato crop grown in a CLS without the use of ISEs. This similarity supports the notion that the ISE-NUTRISENSE system further improves N nutrition in CLS compared to the current practices based on fertigation systems with 2 + 1 concentrated solution tanks.

The improved nutrient status in the root zone of the plants achieved by use of the ISE-NUTRISENSE system was clearly reflected in the leaf nutrient concentrations. In the control treatment, the leaf total-N decreased significantly at the last two sampling dates, although it remained within the sufficient range of 45–55 mg g⁻¹ (Mills and Bryson, 2015). In contrast, in the ISE-NUTRISENSE treatment, it remained constant at the higher initial values. The leaf [K⁺] in the ISE-NUTRISENSE treatment remained constant within the optimal range of 30–60 mg g⁻¹ (Campbell, 2000; Sonneveld and Voogt, 2009), while in the control it followed a decreasing trend after the middle of the growing

season, presumably because of lower concentrations in the root environment. Nitrogen and potassium play important roles in the physiology of plant nutrition and their metabolic functions are closely related to plant productivity (Hawkesford et al., 2012). Hence, the lower yield in the control might be partly ascribed to the lower concentrations of N and/or K in plant tissues. Total soluble solids content (TSSC) is also positively related to K supply in tomato (Almeselmani et al., 2009; Kaur et al., 2018). The increased TSSC in tomato fruits collected from the ISE-NUTRISENSE treatment can be mainly attributed to the higher $[K^+]$ in the RS/DS compared to the control, and consequently to the higher K^+ uptake rates, as indicated by the higher leaf K levels. Furthermore, the decrease in leaf Ca and Mg concentrations on the last sampling date may also have influenced yield performance. Tomato is a demanding plant for Ca, which is involved in cell wall and membrane stabilisation, while Mg plays a crucial role in photosynthesis, as part of chlorophyll, ATP synthesis and enzyme activation (Hawkesford et al., 2012).

In the current study, the $[Na^+]$ in the raw water used to prepare SS was low (0.6 mM) and thus, the accumulation of $[Na^+]$ in the DS/RS did not exceed a level of about 4.5–5 mM in both treatments, which is fully safe for tomato (Sonneveld and Voogt, 2009; Giannothanasis et al., 2024a). This indicates that the nutrient to water uptake ratio (mM), commonly termed uptake concentration (Gallardo et al., 2021), increased to 0.6 mM when the $[Na^+]$ in the RS/DS reached a level of roughly 4.5–5 mM. However, the $[Na^+]$ in the raw water used for SS preparation is frequently higher than 0.6 mM, resulting in accumulation of sodium to higher levels than in the current study (Varlagas et al., 2010; Barbagli et al., 2021). Under such conditions, it has been suggested to gradually reduce the target nutrient concentrations in the RS to compensate for the $[Na^+]$ accumulation (Voogt et al., 2021; Giannothanasis et al., 2024a). In these cases, the importance of the Na^+ ISE to daily monitor its concentration in the RS/DS is increased. However, further research is needed to test the performance of the ISE-NUTRISENSE system when the $[Na^+]$ in the raw water used to prepare SS for CLS is higher than in the current study, resulting in substantial Na^+ accumulation in the RS.

6. Conclusions

The ISE-NUTRISENSE system developed as a prototype and tested in the current study, accurately maintained the concentrations of K^+ , Ca^{2+} , NO_3^- and Mg^{2+} in the root and drainage solution (RS/DS) close to the target values with less than $\pm 10\%$ deviation. The success of the system was due to i) the high accuracy and the rapid measurement procedure of the four ISEs ii) the high performance of the algorithms deployed by the NUTRISENSE DSS and iii) the inclusion of 8 + 1 single-fertiliser concentrated solutions in the system which allowed for accurate implementation of the algorithm output every day. Compared with the

standard practice of injecting nutrients from 2 + 1 concentrated solutions with composition modified weekly or biweekly after a laboratory analysis of the DS (control), the application of the ISE-NUTRISENSE system in a long-term tomato crop grown in a CLS provided clear benefits. More specifically, the ISE-NUTRISENSE system maintained macronutrient concentrations and their mutual ratios in the DS more closely to the target values with substantially smaller fluctuations over time, compared to the control treatment. As a result, the ISE-NUTRISENSE system increased the fruit yield by 7.6 %, the total soluble solids content in fruit by 6.8 %, and the agronomic efficiency of nitrogen by 23 % compared to the control.

The concept applied with the ISE-NUTRISENSE system constitutes a breakthrough for the management of nutrition in CLS as it enables accurate daily readjustment of the nutrient supply based on the current nutrient concentrations in the recycled DS. Therefore, the ISE-NUTRISENSE and similar systems are expected to fully replace the current concept of readjusting the individual nutrient supply weekly or biweekly, using measurements from DS samples that have been collected several days before, and a fertigation system with 2 + 1 concentrated solution tanks.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Evangelos Giannothanasis: Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Juan Cedeno:** Validation, Investigation. **Georgia Ntatsi:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation. **Rodney B. Thompson:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Dimitrios Savvas:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Software, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Abbreviations

AS	added solution
CLS	closed-loop soilless systems
DAT	days after transplanting
DS	drainage solution (effluent)
DSS	decision support system
EC	Electrical conductivity
ISE	ion selective electrode
RS	root solution
SS	supply solution

Nomenclature

i	denotes one of the following nutrients: K^+ , Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , NH_4^+ , NO_3^- , $H_2PO_4^-$, SO_4^{2-}
C_{da}	is the actual target concentration (mM) of the i nutrient in the RS and the DS

C_{dt}	is the standard target concentration (mM) of the i nutrient in the RS and the DS
C_{sr}	is the readjusted (i.e., the actual target) concentration (mM) of the i nutrient in the SS (calculated every day using Equation (9))
C_{st}	is the standard target concentration (mM) of the i nutrient for the SS (according to credible literature sources included in the database of the DSS)
C_w	is the concentration (mM) of the i nutrient in the raw water
C_{im}	is the concentration (mM) of the i nutrient in the water-DS mixture
$\Delta C_s = C_{sr} - C_{st}$	is the change in the concentration of the i nutrient in the SS needed to readjust its concentration in the RS and the DS from C_{da} to C_{dt}
C_{nr}	is the daily readjusted injection rate of the i nutrient to the water-DS mixture, needed to achieve C_{sr}
V_d	is the volume sum (L) of RS and DS per plant
V_a	is the volume (L) of supplied AS per plant per day (net supply of NS excluding the resupply of DS)
M_i	is the total mass (mmol per plant) of the i nutrient
ΣC_i^+	is the sum of the concentrations of K^+ , Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , NH_4^+ , and Na^+ (mM) in the DS
ΣC_i^-	is the sum of the concentrations of NO_3^- , SO_4^{2-} , P , HCO_3^- , and Cl^- (mM) in the DS
ΣC_{im}^+	is the sum of the concentrations of K^+ , Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , NH_4^+ , and Na^+ (mM) in the water-DS mixture
E	denotes the EC ($dS\ m^{-1}$)
E_m	is the EC ($dS\ m^{-1}$) of the water-DS mixture
E_{sr}	is the readjusted EC value ($dS\ m^{-1}$) in the final SS
a	is the fraction of DS (referring to the total volume of SS) that is recycled

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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